

THE INFLUENCE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING AND SELF-EFFICACY ON THE INNOVATIVE BEHAVIOR OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN DEPOK

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of the principal's transformational leadership, school organizational learning, and teacher self-efficacy on the innovative behavior of elementary school teachers in the city of Depok. The research was conducted using quantitative methods. Data was collected using a survey method by filling out the instrument in the form of a questionnaire. The sample in this study amounted to 166 teachers who were obtained using cluster sampling techniques, simple random sampling and proportional sampling. Data processing using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach with SmartPLS software. The results of the study state that: 1) transformational leadership has a significant effect on innovative behavior. 2) Organizational learning has a significant effect on innovative behavior. 3) self-efficacy has a significant effect on innovative behavior. 4) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational learning. 5) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on self-efficacy. 6) Organizational learning has a significant effect on self-efficacy. 7) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on innovative behavior through organizational learning. 8) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on innovative behavior through self-efficacy. 9) Organizational learning has a significant effect on innovative behavior through self-efficacy. 10) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on self-efficacy through organizational learning. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that innovative behavior can be developed through increased transformational leadership, organizational learning, and self-efficacy

Keyword: Transformational leadership, Organizational learning, Self-efficacy, Innovative behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

In education, innovation can emerge as new pedagogic theories, methodological approaches, teaching techniques, learning tools, learning processes, or institutional structures that when applied result in significant changes in teaching and learning that lead to better student learning. So, innovations in education are intended to increase productivity and efficiency of learning and / or improve the quality of learning (Serdyukov, 2017). Teachers in schools today are required to be more innovative in order to improve the quality of education and the effectiveness and efficiency in learning. Innovative teachers tend to be able to find new strategies or methods in delivering material to students, especially students who have different absorption abilities. This must be underlined that each class has a different composition of students, as well as each class with another class must have a different learning absorption. Teachers who often apply new things and can increase students' passion for learning are

teachers who have innovative behaviors in teaching. In order to find a preliminary picture in the study, researchers distributed questionnaires to 11 elementary schools, each representing 11 sub-districts in Depok city, and the school chosen was the school that had the largest teacher population in each sub-district. Each school appointed 5 teachers as the initial sample of the study so that the number of teachers who participated in the initial study was 55 teachers and given 20 statements for each variable.

Table 1. 1 Determination of the number of initial samples of the study.

No.	District	Public Elementary Schools	Sample
1	Limo	SDN Grogol 1	5
2	Sukmajaya	SDN Mekarjaya 13	5
3	Bojongsari	SDN Bojongsari 1	5
4	Cipayung	SDN Citayam 1	5
5	Cimanggis	SDN Tugu 1	5
6	Cilodong	SDN Cilodong 1	5
7	Sawangan	SDN Sawangan 1	5
8	Cinere	SDN Cinere 1	5
9	Pancoran Mas	SDN Depok Jaya 1	5
10	Beji	East Beji Elementary School 1	5
11	Tapos	SDN Sukamaju Baru 2	5
Sum			55

Data from Figure 1. 1 can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.** which is the result of pre-research on the innovative behavior of public elementary school teachers in Depok city. The average figure shows that in the process of innovation from exploring ideas, generating ideas, fighting for ideas, and implementing ideas, there is a decrease in the process. The implementation of an idea is very important because innovation is an idea that has been implemented with a positive purpose, when an idea has not been implemented, it cannot be called an innovation. The average total score of innovative behavior is 3.25. By referring to assessments conducted using a 1-5 grading scale, the numbers show that teachers' innovative behavior is still low.

Figure 1. 1 Results of preliminary Research on Innovative Behavior of Teachers

To support the occurrence of innovative teacher behavior, a leadership role of the principal is needed that can guide teachers to continue to innovate in solving various problems in schools. The type of leadership that is predicted to improve teachers' innovative behavior is transformational leadership. In an academic environment, transformational leadership can lead to changes in strategy and structure similar to those seen in business organizations (Yu et al., 2002). Innovative work behaviors can be driven by transformational leaders by involving employees in different learning activities and allowing them to develop alternative solutions to workplace problems (Li et al., 2019).

The results of preliminary research on the transformational leadership of public elementary school principals in Depok city, the data can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page**Error! Bookmark not defined.**. From this figure, the average value on the indicator of transformational leadership variables, while the average of transformational leadership variables is 3.31 which indicates that the figure is still low when viewed from the assessment scale of 1-5.

Furthermore, a factor that is predicted to improve teachers' innovative behavior is organizational learning. The results of research from Lin and Lee (2017), state that management needs to see organizational learning as the core of innovation, utilizing knowledge sharing projects for explicit knowledge transfer and sharing between members within the organization. This is very helpful for potential innovation and the generation of innovative behaviors employees will follow the process of generational ideas, advocacy, and implementation to realize innovative behaviors. There are several characteristics that indicate the desire or occurrence of an organization that wants to continue to develop through learning such as having a commitment to learning, having a common vision, an open mind/view and sharing knowledge with fellow members of the organization. With strong learning school organizations are expected to improve the innovative behavior of teachers.

The results of preliminary research on the learning of public elementary school organizations in Depok city can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the data can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page**Error! Bookmark not defined.**. From this figure, it can be seen that the average value on the indicator of organizational learning variables, while the average organizational learning variable is 3.07 which indicates that the figure is still low when viewed from the assessment scale of 1-5.

Then the factor that is predicted to affect the innovative behavior of teachers is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy has characteristics, namely: ability to do tasks, complete tasks, face risk challenges, and confidence in improving performance. A person will be considered effective if he is able to solve problems appropriately and continue to explore his potential by continuing to learn. Teachers who have high self-efficacy have a high passion for work/teaching, are ready to accept new ideas/curricula, so that they can use new methods in learning more effectively (Khayati and Sarjana, 2015). With high efficacy, it is hoped that it will affect the innovative behavior of teachers who require a high passion for work and are willing to start new ideas at work to create a new method of work.

The results of preliminary research on the self-efficacy of public elementary school teachers in Depok city can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the data can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page**Error! Bookmark not defined.**. From this figure, it can be seen that the average value on the indicator of self-efficacy variables, while the average of self-efficacy variables is 3.39 which indicates that the figure is still low when viewed from a rating scale of 1-5. In this study, factors that are predicted to influence the innovative behavior of teachers will be studied, both internal and external factors, these factors can be in the form of school leadership, the organizational environment at work, and internal factors of the teacher himself. From the leadership factor, the researcher focuses on the transformational leadership variable, then from the organizational factor the researcher chooses the organizational learning variable, while from the internal factors the researcher uses the self-efficacy variable.

Innovative behavior cannot be separated from creativity, because innovation is creativity that generates ideas that are useful to individuals and groups (Jennifer and Gareth, 2008: 143).

Figure 2. 1 Dimension of Innovation

Source: (Jennifer and Garet, 2008: 143)

The first step is to identify problems that occur in daily work, the second is to try to collect information to solve the problem, the third step is to generate creative ideas to solve the problem, the fourth step is to choose the creative ideas that are considered the most effective, the fifth is the implementation of the creative ideas so as to produce new innovations in the face of a problem. Innovative Behavior is the application of something unique and new to be applied in its work, innovative behavior includes not only the behavior of innovation in the definition of personal work, but also includes the creation and implementation of innovations in the employee's department or at the organizational level, "innovative behavior as an employee's intentional introduction or application of new ideas, products, processes, and procedures to his or her work role, work unit, or organization" (Feirong and Richard 2010). Developing and implementing new work systems, keeping abreast of the latest technological developments and innovations, creating new strategies that will allow to achieve targets, finding new resources to support the implementation of new ideas and efforts to protect these ideas are taken into account in the context of innovative behavior of members and employees of the organization. Innovative behavior has several processes namely: 1) opportunity creation, 2) resource acquisition, 3) implementation and promotion, and 4) application process. Innovative behavior is divided into 3 stages namely: 1) problem recognition, 2) looking for problem-solving ideas and seeking support, 3) building innovation models (Scott and Bruce,

1994). By doing this system, organizations can give birth to ideas for problem solving and apply them in their work. The previous 28 papers were on innovation and creativity and concluded that individual innovative behavior includes five constituent elements that are 1) opportunity exploration, 2) generativity, 3) formative investigation, 4) championing, and 5) application (Kleysen and Street, 2001).

According to Hell Riegel and Slocum (2011: 151), states that "self-efficacy is the individuals estimate of his or her own ability to perform a specific task in a particular situation", an individual's estimation of his own ability to perform a particular task in a particular situation. The greater the perceived ability of employees to perform tasks, the higher Self-efficacy. Employees with high self-efficacy believe that (1) they have the required abilities, (2) they are able to make the necessary efforts, and (3) there are no outside events which would make them unable to perform at a high level.

Self-efficacy has three dimensions, namely (1) magnitude (or level), (2) strength and (3) general state. Lenz and Bagged (2002: 23), explain the magnitude/level (level of difficulty) refers to how difficult a person finds to adopt a particular behavior. This aspect has implications for the selection of behaviors that individuals will try based on their understanding of the difficulty of the task. If the tasks imposed on the individual are arranged according to the degree of difficulty, then the difference in individual self-efficacy may be limited to simple, intermediate tasks or high. The individual will seek to perform tasks that are considered enforceable and avoid situations and behaviors that are beyond the limits of his ability. Strength reflects how confident a person is capable of performing a particular task, this aspect has to do with the strength in a person's belief in his abilities. Strong and steady expectations in individuals will encourage them to be persistent in striving to achieve goals, even if they may not have had a supportive experience.

Organizational learning is an important factor for the long-term performance of the organization and the survival of the organization, "organizational learning is an important determinant of long-term performance and survival for organizations" (Yukl, 2009)

Figure 2. 2 Dimensions of Organizational Learning

Source: (Akuzum, 2014)

Organizational learning is a continuous process of activity that sees learning as fundamental to an organization by paying attention to learning commitment, sharing vision, open mind, and knowledge transfer with the Lin and Lee organization (2017).

According to Hellriegel and Slocum (2011: 329).

Transformational leadership involves anticipating future trends, inspiring followers to understand and embrace a new vision of possibilities, developing others to be leaders or better leaders, and building the organization or group into a community of challenged and rewarded learners. Transformational leadership is a leader who anticipates future trends, inspires followers to understand and embrace new visions of possibilities, develops others to become better leaders or leaders, and builds an organization or group into a community of challenged and valued learners.

II. METHOD

The research method used is to use a quantitative-causal approach using the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) application. In this study, there were 3 exogenous variables, namely X1: transformational leadership, X2: organizational learning, X3: self-efficacy, and one endogenous variable Y: innovative behavior. This study aims to determine the influence between exogenous variables on endogenous variables and the influence of mediation between exogenous variables on endogenous variables through other exogenous variables as intermediate variables.

The analysis unit in this study is a public elementary school in the city of Depok, West Java, and the respondents in this study are teachers of public elementary schools in Depok city. The number of public elementary schools in Depok city reached 207 schools with 7303 teachers, because the population was very large, researchers used the cluster sampling sample technique.

Data collection techniques are carried out using the deployment of instruments with a rating scale. The instrument is an elaboration of the dimensions of each variable. Each dimension is then redefined into the form of an indicator. After that, instruments are made based on existing indicators. The instrument is tested first before being used in research. The test of the instrument includes validity tests and reliability tests, from the test results obtained valid and invalid instrument items. Invalid instruments will be discarded or not used in the study, while items of valid instruments will be used in the research process.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The measurement model includes reflective and formative model measurements. By calculating in the PLS algorithm analyzes the measurement model between free variables and bound variables to evaluate the validity, reliability, and test of classical assumptions.

Validity Testing Convergent Validity. Convergent validity can be assessed by looking at the value of the outer loading or loading factor. The criterion of good convergent validity if the outer loading value > 0.7 , but so in the research stage of scale development, loading 0.50 to 0.60 is still acceptable (Ghozali, 2021: 35).

Table 4. 1 Outer Loading

Variable	Indicators	Loading Factor	Variable	Indicators	Loading Factor
Innovative Behavior	PI11	0.809	Efficacy Diri	ED8	0.755
	PI12	0.805		ED17	0.791
	PI16	0.799		ED19	0.82
	PI17	0.783		ED20	0.768
	PI 19	0.813		ED21	0.764
	PI 21	0.796		ED22	0.828
	PI 24	0.717	Leadership	KT11	0.833
	PI 31	0.705		KT21	0.771
	PI 33	0.744		KT26	0.812
	PI 36	0.713		KT31	0.795
Organizational Learning	PO18	0.744	KT36	0.781	
	PO19	0.72	KT37	0.821	
	PO22	0.731			
	PO23	0.728			
	PO24	0.791			
	PO34	0.736			
	PO35	0.831			
	PO37	0.722			

The results of the validity test can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page**Error! Bookmark not defined.**, the test was carried out using a convergent validity test technique which aims to determine the level of respondent's understanding of the instrument by paying attention to the valid loading factor value if it > from 0.7. Based on the values in Table 4. 1 all outer loading values are declared valid and it can be known that there are 10 indicators that represent innovative behavior variables, 8 indicators for organizational learning variables, 6 indicators for self-efficacy behavior and 6 indicators for transformational leadership variables.

Discriminant Validity

Then the discriminant validity test is carried out by looking at the cross loading value which must get an average variance extracted (AVE) value of > 0.5 to be declared valid (Ghozali, 2021: 37).

Table 4. 2 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Ave
Innovative Behavior	0.592
Organizational Learning	0.564

Self-efficacy	0.621
Transformational Leadership	0.644

In Table 4. 2 AVE values indicate that the value of each variable is more than 0.5, this reflects that the discriminant validity is good, and the model can be used because the validity test conditions are met. The results of the calculation of the AVE value can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**

Figure 4. 1 AVE Graphics

Composite Reliability

Next is the Reliability test by looking at the Cronbach alpha value or by looking at the composite reliability value. The goal is to find out the consistency of the data with a reliable criterion of > 0.7 .

Table 4. 3 Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Innovative Behavior	0.924	0.935
Organizational Learning	0.89	0.912
Self-efficacy	0.879	0.908
Transformational Leadership	0.889	0.916

Based on Table 4. 3 which is the result of the calculation in **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.** cro value of nbach alpha and a composite reliability value of > 0.7 which proves that all variables are said to be reliable and the model can be used.

Figure 4. 2Cronbach Alpha Diagram

Test Classical Assumptions

From Table 4. 4 by looking at the variance inflation factor (VIF) value from **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.** it is known that all values < 5 signify the absence of multicollinearity, that is, the absence of correlations between free variables that can cause the magnitude of the standard error and a small t count (Ghozali, 2021: 72).

Table 4. 4 Outer VIF Values

Variable	Indicators	VIFs	Variable	Indicators	VIFs	
Innovative Behavior	PI11	2.962	Self-efficacy	ED8	1.626	
	PI12	2.719		ED17	2.392	
	PI16	2.649		ED19	2.691	
	PI17	2.730		ED20	2.183	
	PI19	2.600		ED21	1.920	
	PI21	2.352		ED22	2.348	
	Organizational Learning	PI24	2.003	Transformational Leadership	KT11	2.308
		PI31	2.003		KT21	1.997
		PI33	2.552		KT26	2.159
		PI36	2.681		KT31	2.040
PO18	2.155	KT36	1.918			
PO19	2.156	KT37	2.420			
PO22	2.064					
PO23	2.086					

	PO24	2.062			
	PO34	1.905			
	PO35	2.717			
	PO37	1.756			

Structural Model Testing (inner model)

The structural model (inner model) is the result of analysis using the calculate PLS algorithm in the PLS program which is shown in Figure 4. Figure 4. 3 this figure, you can see the R square value on the circle and the coefficient path value on the arrow.

Figure 4. 3 Structural Model (PLS Algorithm)

Model Due Diligence

The feasibility test of the model is carried out by looking at the value of the R square which is the goodness-fit test of the model in **Error! Reference source not found.** hal 229, values above 0.67 are said to be **Error! Bookmark not defined.** (Ghozali, 2021: 75)

Table 4. 5 R Square

Variable	R Square
Innovative Behavior	0.550
Organizational Learning	0.059
Self-efficacy	0.276

Based on the results seen from Table 4. 5 which is the result of the calculations in **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**, it is presented that the R value of the innovative behavior square is 0. 550, that means the variables of transformational leadership, organizational learning, and self-efficacy have an influence of 55% on the variables of innovative behavior and explain that the influence is moderate. Next is the R square value of organizational learning of 0. 059, that means the transformational leadership variable has an influence of 5.9% on the organizational learning variable and explains that the influence is weak. The three values of R square self-efficacy of 0.276 that means the transformational leadership variable have an influence of 27.6% on the self-efficacy variable and explain that the influence is weak.

Figure 4. 4 R Square Graphics

Evaluation of the construct model can also be done by evaluating the value of Q square which describes how well the observation value generated by the model and shows the estimation of its parameters. Models that have predictive values are relevant if the Q square value > 0 (Ghozali, 2021: 76). Predictive relevance values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 indicate that the model is weak, medium, and strong. The value of Q square can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** page **Error! Bookmark not defined.** which is the result of blindfolding analysis on PLS programs, innovative behavior has a value of 0.310 (moderate), self-efficacy 0.159 (moderate), and organizational learning 0.03 (weak). All variables have predictive relevance because the indigo Q square > 0.

The results of the calculation of the influence of transformational leadership on the innovative behavior of teachers show that $(9,050) > (1.96)$ and $(0.00) < (a 0.05)$, then rejected and accepted. While the direction of influence is positive (0.502). Thus it can be concluded that transformational leadership (X1) has a significant effect on innovative behavior (Y).

The results of this study are in line with previously conducted research that explains transformational leadership can stimulate employees to see problems in a new way (intellectual stimulation) and can motivate employees to complete creatively (inspirational motivation) (Shin and Zhou, 2017). Likewise, research conducted in schools by Ahamad and Kasim (2016), transformational is reported to have a great influence on the behavior of individuals in organizations. This study aims to identify the influence of the transformational leadership of principals on the innovative behavior of teachers in schools. The results show that transformational leadership principals have influenced teachers' innovative behavior. The results of research conducted by Bawuro et al. (2018), explained that innovative behavior refers to the process of developing, generating, implementing or promoting new ideas by employees to improve work performance. Today, rapid social and technological changes in our environment highlight the importance of innovative behavior of employees and especially for teachers. The findings suggest that happiness in the workplace, organizational climate, affective commitment and transformational leadership play a direct role in influencing behavior innovative.

Transformational leadership thinking provokes the individual to generate new ideas and develop individual potential (Kahai et al., 2003). Several studies show that transformational leaders empower and provide an innovative climate for their followers, in a study studying 32 companies in Taiwan found there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and organizational innovation (Jung et al., 2003). Gumusluolu and Ilsev (2009), found that the transformational role of leaders increases organizational innovation. A study found that transformational leadership has encouraged creativity among employees within the organization.

Transformational leadership is able to recognize the needs of followers to change, create a vision and lead change and implement change effectively (Sosik et al., 2010). The results of research from Muzafary et al. (2019), explain that innovative work behavior is increasingly vital for the survival of the organization. Transformational leadership has become very active in influencing followers in improving innovative work behaviors. Psychological empowerment as an enhancer of the influence of transformational leadership and found that transformational leadership acts through empowerment to influence the results of individual work. The study recognizes that transformational leadership fully influences the work behavior of innovation, which consists in the formation of ideas and the implementation of ideas.

IV. Conclusion

This study examines the influence of the principal's transformational leadership, school organizational learning, and teacher self-efficacy on the innovative behavior of elementary school teachers in Depok city. Based on the analysis and discussion of researchers, it can be concluded that:

1. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on teachers' innovative behaviors. Principals who remind of the school's vision, supervise, direct teachers to work with

technology, are willing to listen to teachers' complaints, reward teachers, and play a role as mentors will produce teachers who discover and champion innovative opportunities, create, promote and apply new techniques, promote and apply new methods, fight for and implement solutions to problems. Transformational leadership behavior is very important for principals to generate respect for leaders who can influence their idealism, inspirational motivation, can provide intellectual stimulation, and give its individual consideration to teachers.

2. Organizational learning has a significant effect on innovative behavior. When the school provides a good organizational or team in conducting learning with peers, a team will be formed that is hungry for learning and individuals who have a high commitment to continue learning. In a team, there is also an exchange of visions by teachers with an open mind, how they should deal with various changes such as curriculum changes or changes in online teaching methods as happened during the pandemic era. With the establishment of an atmosphere of sharing good knowledge among teachers, it will have an impact on increasing teachers' innovative behavior.
3. Self-efficacy has a significant effect on innovative behavior. When the teacher has the strength and is resistant to all obstacles, it will spur the teacher to work and increase the teacher's confidence in facing all changes. Teachers who complete tasks according to the target, are diligent in working, able to work under pressure are the characteristics of teachers who have high self-efficacy. Teachers must have confidence in their own abilities in dealing with various problems at work, adapt to all forms of change to improve innovative behavior teacher.
4. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational learning. The implication of these findings is a reference for the principal to increase his influence, motivation, stimulation, and individual consideration to support the learning of the teacher's organization. With this learning platform, it can help the principal in conveying information about learning plans or about changes that occur in the world of education, so that teachers get provisions in learning the difficulties faced or be able to adapt to the changes that occur.
5. Transformational leadership has a significant effect on self-efficacy. The principal must use his influence to mobilize the teacher, able to motivate the teacher to be able to increase the self-confidence of the teacher. The greater the principal's ability to motivate teachers, the more powerful the teacher will be in dealing with problems or workloads. With intellectual stimulation the principal can also give a good opinion or input when the teacher faces difficulties or changes in work.

REFERENCE

1. Abdullah, A. G. K., Ling, Y.-L., & Kader, Z. B. S. A. (2016). View of PRINCIPAL'S TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND TEACHER'S CREATIVITY: MEDIATING ROLE OF SELF EFFICACY. *Management Research Journal* Vol. 6, No. 1 (2016), 1 -7. <http://ojs.upsi.edu.my/index.php/MRJ/article/view/1426/1053>

2. Afsar, B., & Masood, M. (2017). Transformational Leadership, Creative Self-Efficacy, Trust in Supervisor, Uncertainty Avoidance, and Innovative Work Behavior of Nurses: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886317711891>, 54(1), 36–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886317711891>
3. Ahamad, Z.bin, & Eunuch, A. L.bin. (2016). The Effects of Transformational Leadership towards Teachers Innovative Behavior in Schools. www.ijsrp.org
4. Akuzum, C. (2014). Knowledge inertia and organizational learning as the explanation of organizational performance. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 9(21), 1143–1155. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2014.1885>
5. Amo, B. W., & Kolvereid, L. (2011, November 21). *Organizational Strategy, Individual Personality and Innovation Behavior*. World Scientific; World Scientific Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218495805000033>
6. Axtell, C. M., Holman, D. J., & Unsworth, K. L. (2000). Shopfloor innovation: Facilitating the suggestion and implementation of ideas. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(3), 265–285. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317900167029>
7. Bawuro, F. A., Danjuma, I., & Wajiga, H. (2018). Factors Influencing Innovative Behaviour of Teachers in Secondary Schools in the North East of Nigeria. *Path of Science*, 4(3), 1007–1017. <https://doi.org/10.22178/POS.32-9>
8. Bratianu, C. (2018). Organizational Learning and the Learning Organization. *Organizational Knowledge Dynamics: Managing Knowledge Creation, Acquisition, Sharing, and Transformation*. , 286–312. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-8318-1.CH012>
9. Braun, S., Peus, C., Weisweiler, S., & Frey, D. (2013). Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and team performance: A multilevel mediation model of trust. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 24(1), 270–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LEAQUA.2012.11.006>
10. Calantone, R. J., Cavusgil, S. T., & Zhao, Y. (2002). Learning orientation, firm innovation capability, and firm performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 31(6), 515–524. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501\(01\)00203-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501(01)00203-6)
11. Chen, G., Gully, S. M., & Eden, D. (2001). Validation of a New General Self-Efficacy Scale. *Organizational Research Methods*, 4(1), 62–83. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442810141004>
12. Darmanah, G. (2019). RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Hira Tech. www.hira-tech.com
13. Dhita, S. (2019, August 22). 70 percent of teachers are incompetent. [Pikiran-Rakyat.Com](https://www.pikiran-rakyat.com/pendidikan/pr-01317844/70-guru-tidak-kompeten). <https://www.pikiran-rakyat.com/pendidikan/pr-01317844/70-guru-tidak-kompeten> (January 14, 2022).
14. Eden, D. (1992, December 1). Leadership and expectations: Pygmalion effects and other self-fulfilling prophecies in organizations. *The Leadership Quarterly*; Jai. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(92\)90018-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(92)90018-B)
15. Endang, M. (2011). *Applied Research in Education and Engineering* (1st ed., Vol. 1). UNY Press. <http://staffnew.uny.ac.id/upload/132296045/lainlain/buku-riset-terapan-apri.pdf>
16. Fauzy, A. (2019). *Sampling Method* (2nd ed., Vol. 1). Open University. https://pak.uui.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/B1-Buku-1-ok_Metode-Sampling.pdf
17. Feirong, Y., & Richard, W. W. (2010). Innovative behavior in the workplace: the role of performance and image outcome expectations. In *Academy of Management Journal*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25684323>
18. Fernández-Mesa, A., Alegre-Vidal, J., Chiva-Gómez, R., & Gutiérrez-Gracia, A. (2012). Design Management Capability: Its mediating Role between OLC and Innovation Performance in SMEs. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/36179878.pdf>

19. García-Morales, V. J., Jiménez-Barrionuevo, M., & Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez, L. (2012). Transformational leadership influence on organizational performance through organizational learning and innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(7), 1040–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.03.005>
20. Ghozali, I. (2021). *Partial Least Squares (concept, technique and application)* (A. Tejokusumo (ed.); 3rd ed.). Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
21. Gibson, J. L., Ivancevich, J. M., & James H. Donnelly, J. (2012). *Organizations Behavior, Structure, Processes*. In *Syria Studies* (14th ed., Vol. 7, Issue 1). McGraw-Hill. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269107473_What_is_governance/link/548173090cf22525dcb61443/download%0Ahttp://www.econ.upf.edu/~reynal/Civil_wars_12December2010.pdf%0Ahttps://think-asia.org/handle/11540/8282%0Ahttps://www.jstor.org/stable/41857625
22. Gozukara, I., & Yildirim, O. (2016). Exploring the link between Distributive Justice and Innovative Behavior: Organizational Learning Capacity as a Mediator. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting*, 6(2), 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARAFMS/v6-i2/2042>
23. Gumusluolu, L., & Ilsev, A. (2009). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Innovation: The Roles of Internal and External Support for Innovation*. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 26(3), 264–277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1540-5885.2009.00657.X>
24. Hellriegel, D., & Slocum, J. W. (2011). *Organizational behavior*. South-Western Cengage Learning.
25. Hollenbeck, J. R., & W. I. J. A. (2009). *Organizational Behavior*. https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Organizational_Behavior/Hs2NAgAAQBAJ?hl=id&gbpv=1&dq=Organizational+Behavior:+Securing+Competitive+Advantage&printsec=frontcover